

MANY FACTORS RELATING TO PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS

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Annotation. The goal of the research is to examine the syntax and semantics of English paremiological units using content from the "labor-idleness" thematic group. The article sets and completes the following tasks: to define the term "paremiological unit" and to describe the many components of these units, which are a part of the linguistics field known as paremiology. The doctoral thesis' anticipated outcomes will advance linguistics, paremiology, linguistic folklore, comparative linguistics, and linguoculture theory. The study's findings will be put to use in the delivery of seminars and scientific courses, as well as in the reading of English-language lectures and specialized courses.

Keywords: paremiological units, semantics, English language, linguistics, philology.

Аннотация. Цель исследования - изучить синтаксис и семантику английских паремиологических единиц с использованием контента из тематической группы «труд-безделье». В статье поставлены и выполнены следующие задачи: дать определение термину «паремиологическая единица» и описать множество компонентов этих единиц, входящих в состав области языкознания, известной как паремиология. Ожидаемые результаты докторской диссертации будут способствовать развитию лингвистики, паремиологии, лингвистического фольклора, сравнительной лингвистики и теории лингвокультуры. Результаты исследования будут использованы при проведении семинаров и научных курсов, а также при чтении лекций и специализированных курсов на английском языке.

Ключевые слова: паремиологические единицы, семантика, английский язык, языкознание, филология.

Introduction. This essay is focused on the issue of a thorough explanation of paremiological units from a philological perspective. Since ancient times, paremiological units have been extensively used in society. People did not have the option to express their opinions in writing in ancient times. They were required to memorize memorable phrases resembling the paremiological units. As a result, these proverbs became accepted as part of society and were passed down orally from generation to generation. These proverbs were then given the label "paremia" or "paremiological unit." The scientific term for this term is "paremeological unit,"

however it is more commonly referred to as "proverbs and sayings" by the general public¹. According to Soviet folklorist G.L. Permyakov, proverbs are first and foremost linguistic phenomena made up of regular utterances that resemble phrases. They also serve as logical units that express certain meanings. Thirdly, proverbs and sayings are a striking illustration of truth data collected in tiny form.

The language has stable paremia or paremiological units. They can be identified by their rhythm, conciseness, consistency, standards, emotional intensity, imagery, creative representation of their originality regularly, and their long-term effectiveness. Paremiological units are seen to be undervalued in today's society. Numerous accomplishments in the contemporary educational system may result from the study of and comprehension of paremiological units. Despite the long history of philological study of paremiological units, this field of philology is one of those where a fairly stable understanding of the status and semantics of the object under study has not yet been achieved. For a large scientific readership, practically every paremiological unit as well as the entirety of this scientific discipline need explication. The linguistic status and semantic structure of the paremiological units can be regarded as the study's object. The importance of this study is mostly determined by the factors listed above. Any paremiological unit's semantics makes sense if we consider them as a whole. Negative representations and incorrect paramological units do not permeate society. Analogs are composed of paremiological units in a particular setting. Paremiological units have the ability to interpret a straightforward explanation of the circumstance using different vocabulary unrelated to the literal scenario².

Paremiological units that are utilized in related instances but have different semantic shades are distinct. The paremiological units' semantics are rich in wisdom and reflect the way of life of common people through the images they have seen through the years, their perceptions, and occasionally even their flaws and limits. Paremiological units function similarly to a code. It is a fixed rule that cannot be altered. The truth solidifies the socially established values and norms. These enduring societal rules are unbreakable and are not daring. Similar to how it is difficult to disregard the law, it is impossible to dispute the importance of paremiological units. Paremiological units keep an eye on adherence to the tenets of life developed over the ages. The

¹ Baymakhanova T., Otesheva N., Baytoleeva N. (1988). English proverbs and sayings and their equivalents in the Russian and Kazakh languages: The Paremiological Dictionary. AlmaAta: Mektep, - 160 p.

² Ermakova V.A. (2010). Conceptualization of the "own-others" opposition in the paremic picture of the world (on the basis of Russian and English languages). Dissertation abstract in support of candidate for a philology degree // Astana, - 24 p.

younger generation is continually receiving these values from the older age. Paremiological units are brief utterances that are employed in instruction. Both older and younger people are permanently impacted by the paremiological units. A proverb's profound significance causes one to reflect and guides one in the correct direction.

The entire population of a certain civilization is educated by paremiological units from generation to generation, not only the younger age. Paremiological units' primary instructional function is to provide a clear opinion on a given circumstance. It accepts or rejects the action that has been or is about to be taken. As a result, the semantics of this paremia are close to the listener's perception of a particular paremiological unit. A person receives an aesthetic education from the paremiological unit. Teaching people to appreciate the beauty in work, nature, and human activity influences their ability to communicate culturally, act politely, and have high moral standards. Feelings of beauty are crucial to human existence. Reading literary works and paremiological units helps teach aesthetic education since it helps students comprehend their meaning and appreciate the beauty around them. The pre-made complex formulas that make up the paremiological units. It is willing to use several terms that cannot be substituted to convey a certain circumstance. Paremiological units are a well-known word string, just like the intricate formulae employed in calculus.

In linguistics and folklore studies, the paremiological units are investigated as a type of permanent syntax and as a branch of oral folk literature. Perhaps there are many more definitions of paremiological units in general linguistics than there are paremiological units themselves. There are an infinite number of paremiological definitions in every language spoken in the world, according to English linguists and other linguists. The paremiological units were described as follows by Bartlett Jere Whiting in 1932: "A proverb is an expression that, owing its origin to the people, testifies to its origin in form and word. It uses simple language to convey what seems to be a universal truth or truism but is frequently embellished with alliteration and rhyme³. It is typically brief but not always; it is typically accurate but not always. Many proverbs only have one of the two meanings, while some do have both literal and metaphorical interpretations, both of which are perfectly reasonable. A proverb must be venerable, ancient, and have multiple instances of attestation throughout history because these characteristics might be faked by a crafty writer.

³ Esimzhanova M.R. (1998). Interlanguage phraseological correspondences (on the material of the English, Russian and Kazakh languages). Dissertation in support of candidate for a philology degree. Almaty - 128 p.

When dealing with very early literature, where the available material is insufficient, this last criterion must frequently be waived. Another way to define paremiological units is as follows: "A proverb is a common set phrase without an author, mostly understood in different languages, expressing in one sentence a principle, advice, genuine or assumed truth in a general, concise form, its basic idea being of general validity, or at least its user considers it to be such." Paremiological units are defined as follows by German professor U. Mieder: "Proverbs are brief, widely understood sentences of the folk that contains wisdom, truths, morals, and traditional views in a metaphorical, fixed, and memorable form and that are passed down orally from generation to generation."

Conclusion. The location of where a person settles and lives have a strong influence on the language that person speaks. The uniqueness of the English paremiological units is impressive. Particularly, the right words of the people are enigmatically profound and expertly adorn and fascinate everyone. The semantics of the English language depend on paremiological units, just as those of other languages⁴.

Phonetics, grammar, and syntax are also ways that a particular nation's semantics are represented. In general, the meaning of the English paremiological units can be used to infer what a person has observed and comprehended about their life as well as their assessment of it. "Every nation will continue to speak their own language until only their own weather, seasons, natural surroundings, traditional foods, and ethnicity are left. They perpetuate national ideas and realities while feeding the language. Theoretical issues regarding the intricate description of paremiological units were formulated in the paper. In the course of the research, some of these issues were resolved. Paremiological units were regarded as stable, reproducible linguistic events that expressed a certain opinion in specific contexts. By looking at these paremiological units via the lens of phraseology, that is, from the position of fitting their phraseological criteria, the fairly contentious topic of attributing proverbs and sayings to phraseology is resolved. Proverbs and sayings can be attributed to phraseology because of their important characteristics, including their stability in terms of composition, structure, and meaning. The first thing that paremiological units do is express a clear attitude toward a certain occurrence that is currently occurring. However, the fact that the saying chosen as an example and point of comparison is not arbitrary; rather, it is representative of common circumstances and characteristics. As a result, the issue of describing the

⁴ Osheva E.A. (2013). Linguocultural specificity of the paremiological space: on the basis of Russian and English. Dissertation abstract in support of candidate for a philology degree / Perm, 21 p.

paremiological unit's semantics was taken into consideration. Proverbs and sayings are formal equivalents to sentences, but they differ in that a sentence can apply to any circumstance depending on specific facts or events.

As paremiological units lose their scientific significance and interest in the contemporary linguistic scientific world, it is advised that researchers conduct further research in this area and apply their findings to the field of teaching foreign languages using paremiological units. In the future, English paremiological units will continue to be thoroughly investigated, and their fresh concepts will be exposed. The paremiological units will be passed on to the following generation in the same form that we utilize them today. It is a treasure that is passed down through the generations. Its intrinsic worth has not been and will not be depleted. The people's enthusiasm for research and education reveals the paremiological units that have developed over the centuries in England. Additionally, it enables English language learners who are learning the language as a foreign language to understand the peculiarities of the paremiological units by analyzing the word sequences of its inner and outer structure as well as the semantics of the paremiological units of English.

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